

OXIDATION OF SULPHYDRYL BODIES BY HYDROGEN PEROXIDE IN PRESENCE OF INORGANIC CATALYSTS.
PART II. OXIDATION OF CYSTINE BY MEANS OF HYDROGEN PEROXIDE IN PRESENCE OF VANADIC ACID SOL.

BY J. C. GHOSH AND B. C. KAR.

In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 485) the oxidation of cystine and dithiodiglycolic acid by means of hydrogen peroxide in presence of tungstic acid and molybdic acid sols has been described. Oxidation of cystine by means of hydrogen peroxide can also be carried out in presence of vanadic acid sol. Cysteic acid has been isolated as the main product of oxidation. Ammonia, sulphuric acid and carbon dioxide in small quantities have also been detected.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Cysteic Acid.

Cystine (2.5 g.) was dissolved in minimum quantity of pure strong hydrochloric acid and 100 c.c. of redistilled water were added. Hydrogen peroxide was added in slight excess, one molecule of cystine requiring five molecules of hydrogen peroxide to form cysteic acid. 0.05M-sodium tungstate (2 c.c.) in the form of sol was then added and the reaction mixture was kept at room temperature (28-30°) with occasional shaking. After a few days when all the cystine was oxidised as shown by its absence when tested with uric acid reagent, the reaction mixture was evaporated slowly in a vacuum desiccator containing sulphuric acid at room temperature. Fine crystals of cysteic acid were obtained which were removed when completely dry by extracting with absolute alcohol and recrystallised from water in a desiccator.

Estimation of Carbon Dioxide.—Carbon dioxide was estimated by the following arrangements as shown in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1.

A and B are two glass stoppered U-tubes filled with soda lime to absorb atmospheric carbon dioxide and C is the reaction chamber fitted with a rubber cork through which the inlet and outlet tubes and a small glass stoppered separating funnel pass. D and E contain calcium chloride to absorb moisture. F and G are two other glass stoppered U-tubes containing soda lime. In F carbon dioxide from the reaction chamber is absorbed. G is the guard tube. All the tubes are joined by means of pressure tubes and made air-tight by coating the joints with paraffin wax.

Cystine solution (8 c.c.) in hydrochloric acid containing 0.25 g. cystine and hydrogen peroxide solution (5 c.c.) containing peroxide 1.5 times the theoretical amount to form cysteic acid were placed in the reaction chamber and tightly filled. Air was then drawn through the whole apparatus for 1 hour at a slow rate by means of an aspirator to remove the carbon dioxide initially present in the reaction chamber. The soda lime tube F was then very accurately weighed. Freshly prepared sol (2 c.c.) containing 1 c.c. 0.1M sodium tungstate was then introduced through the separating funnel and shaken by bubbling air for a few minutes and allowed to stand at room temperature for 36 hours. After that period carbon dioxide was absorbed in F by drawing air for three hours. On weighing the tube an increase in weight (4.3 mg.) was obtained. The control experiment similarly carried out but without the sol gave an increase in weight of only 0.3 mg.

Ammonia and Sulphuric Acid.—Ammonia and sulphuric acid can be easily detected in the reaction mixture, the former by Nessler's reagent and the latter by barium chloride, keeping suitable control. 0.2 G. of cystine gives about 1 mg. of ammonia after 48 hours.

Kinetics of Reaction.

The methods of investigation are exactly the same as in the case of tungstic acid and molybdic acid sols (*cf.* Ghosh and Kar, *loc. cit.*). The sol was prepared by the addition of dilute hydrochloric acid to chemically pure sodium vanadate a few minutes before the experiment was begun.

No spontaneous decomposition of hydrogen peroxide took place at low concentration of the sol used.

The sol itself liberates iodine from a solution of potassium iodide in sulphuric acid. It has been found that the total amount of iodine liberated by a mixture of sol and hydrogen peroxide is equal to the sum of the two liberated separately.

FIG. 2.

A correlation was, therefore, made in every experiment for the iodine liberated by the sol. The results of kinetic measurements are given below. In all the experiments the concentration of sol is expressed in terms of $NaVO_3$. Table I gives a typical experiment in detail. The velocity is represented by a unimolecular equation of the form,

$$K = \frac{I}{t_2 - t_1} \log \frac{a - x_1}{a - x_2}$$

TABLE I.

Conc. of $H_2O_2 = 0.0385M$. Cystine = $0.00417M$. $NaVO_3 = 0.001M$. $p_H = 1.15$. Volume = 15 c.c. Temp. = 31° . Composition of the reaction mixture: 3 c.c. of cystine + 6 c.c. of HCl + 3 c.c. of sol + 3 c.c. of H_2O_2 .

	Time.	0.01N-thio = 0.504 c.c. of reaction mixture.	K.
	0 min.	3.92 c.c.	
1.	4	3.89	0.0012 (1 & 2)
2.	43	3.68	0.0012 (2 & 3)
3.	88.5	3.46	0.00125 (3 & 4)
4.	128.5	3.28	0.0013 (4 & 5)
5.	172.5	3.10	0.00125 (5 & 6)
6.	231.5	2.90	

Mean 0.00124

TABLE II.

*Effect of varying the concentration of cystine.*Temp. = 31°. $p_H = 1.15$. $\text{NaVO}_3 = 0.001 M$.

Initial conc. of cystine.	Conc. of H_2O_2 .	K (mean).
0.00417M	0.06M	0.00156
0.00834	0.06	0.00108
0.01251	0.058	0.00091

TABLE III.

*Effect of varying the concentration of H_2O_2 .*Temp. = 31°. Cystine = 0.00417M, $\text{NaVO}_3 = 0.001 M$.

Initial conc. of $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2(M)$	$p_H = 1.56$.			$p_H = 1.15$.			
	...	0.0236	0.0481	0.0776	0.0236	0.0385	0.06
K	...	0.0008	0.00085	0.00095	0.00093	0.00124	0.00156

When $1/K$ is plotted graphically against $1/\text{conc. of hydrogen peroxide}$ a straight line is obtained (*cf.* Fig. 2).

TABLE IV.

*Effect of varying the concentration of NaVO_3 .*Temp. = 31°. $p_H = 1.56$.
Cystine = 0.00417M.

Conc. of H_2O_2 .	Conc. of NaVO_3 .	K .
0.0224M	0.0005 M	0.0004
0.0236	0.001	0.0008
0.0243	0.002	0.0015

TABLE V.

Effect of varying the temperature. $p_H = 1.56$. Cystine = 0.00417M.
 $\text{NaVO}_3 = 0.001 M$.

Temp.	Conc. of H_2O_2 .	K .
21°	0.0253 M	0.00037
31°	0.0236	0.00080

TABLE VI.

*Effect of varying the p_{H} .*Temp. = 31°. Cystine = 0.00417M. NaVO_3 = 0.001M.

H_2O_2 (M)	...	0.0236	0.0236	0.0243
p_{H}	...	1.15	1.56	2.3
K	...	0.00093	0.0008	0.00026

Sodium tungstate and ammonium molybdate also catalyse the oxidation of cystine by means of hydrogen peroxide. But unlike them pure sodium vanadate is not capable of catalysing the reaction.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
THE UNIVERSITY,
Dacca.

Received March 31, 1937.